

“STUDYING THE AMINO ACID OF RAPE SQUEEZE GROWN IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN”

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Abstract. As the country's population grows, the need for protein products increases. It is necessary to provide the country's population with food products of increased biological and nutritional value. Various protein-containing additives introduced into food recipes play a huge role in this. One of the sources that increases the nutritional and biological value of food products is rapeseed squeeze.

The purpose of the work was to study the amino acid and aminokislota composition of rapeseed squeeze grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The object of the study was squeezed from rapeseed seeds grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan of the Viking variety. The amino acid composition of rapeseed squeeze proteins was studied according to GOST 32195-2013 [4]. The aminokislota composition of rapeseed seed squeeze grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan was determined using the atomic adsorption method on a solar atomic adsorption spectrometer. S 2. Squeeze from rapeseed grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan contains almost all essential amino acids. Rapeseed seed squeeze contains a high content of leucine (2.28 g /100g), phenylamine (1.2 g /100g), isoleucine (1.03 g/ 100g), methionine (0.87 g/ 100g), tryptophan (0.431 g/ 100g). This indicates that the proteins in rapeseed squeeze have a complete amino acid composition. The aminokislota composition of squeeze from rapeseed seeds grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan is characterized by a high content of P-1116%, magnesium-465%, calcium 232.5%, potassium-77.4%, zinc-9.38% and other macro and microelements. These research data indicate the advisability of using rapeseed squeeze in national dishes of Uzbekistan to increase nutritional and biological value.

Keywords: rapeseed squeeze, protein, amino acid composition, aminokislota composition, macro and microelements, amino acid score, essential amino acids, biological value.

Annotatsiya. Mamlakat aholisining ko'payishi bilan oqsilli mahsulotlarga bo'lgan ehtiyoj ortib bormoqda. Mamlakat aholisini biologik va ozuqaviy qiymati yuqori bo'lgan oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari bilan ta'minlash zarur. Bunda oziq-ovqat retseptlariga kiritilgan turli xil proteinli qo'shimchalar katta rol o'ynaydi. Oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarining ozuqaviy va biologik qiymatini oshiradigan manbalardan biri raps siqmasidir.

Ishning maqsadi O'zbekiston Respublikasida yetishtiriladigan raps siqmasining aminokislotalar tarkibini o'rganish edi. Tadqiqot ob'ekti O'zbekiston Respublikasida yetishtiriladigan “Viking” navli raps urug'idan siqib chiqarildi. Raps siqma oqsillarining aminokislotalar tarkibi GOST 32195-2013 [4] bo'yicha o'rganilgan. O'zbekiston Respublikasida yetishtiriladigan raps urug'ining aminokislota tarkibi quyosh atom adsorbsion spektrometrida atom adsorbsion usuli yordamida aniqlandi. S 2. O'zbekiston Respublikasida yetishtiriladigan raps urug'idan olingan siqma tarkibida deyarli barcha muhim aminokislotalar mavjud. Raps urug'i siqmasida yuqori miqdorda leysin (2,28 g / 100 g), fenilamin (1,2 g / 100 g), izolösin (1,03

g / 100 g), metionin (0,87 g / 100 g), triptofan (0,431 g / 100 g) mavjud. Bu raps siqmasidagi oqsillarning to'liq aminokislota tarkibiga ega ekanligini ko'rsatadi. O'zbekiston Respublikasida yetishtiriladigan raps urug'idan siqmaning aminokislota tarkibi P-1116%, magniy-465%, kaltsiy 232,5%, kaliy-77,4%, rux-9,38% va boshqa makro va mikroelementlarning yuqori miqdori bilan ajralib turadi. Ushbu tadqiqot ma'lumotlari ozuqaviy va biologik qiymatini oshirish uchun O'zbekiston milliy taomlarida raps siqmasidan foydalanish maqsadga muvofiqligini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Raps siqma, oqsil, aminokislotalar tarkibi, aminokislota tarkibi, makro va mikroelementlar, aminokislotalar reytingi, muhim aminokislotalar, biologik qiymati.

Аннотация. С ростом населения страны увеличивается потребность в белковых продуктах. Необходимо обеспечить население страны продуктами питания повышенной биологической и пищевой ценности. Огромную роль в этом играют различные белоксодержащие добавки, вводимые в рецептуры блюд. Одним из источников, повышающих пищевую и биологическую ценность продуктов питания, является рапсовый жом.

Целью работы было изучение аминокислотного и минерального состава рапсового жома, выращенного в Республике Узбекистан. Объектом исследования являлся жом из семян рапса, выращенного в Республике Узбекистан сорта Викинг. Аминокислотный состав белков рапсового жома изучался по ГОСТ 32195-2013 [4]. Минеральный состав рапсового жома, выращенного в Республике Узбекистан, определялся с помощью атомно-адсорбционного метода на солнечном атомно-адсорбционном спектрометре. С 2. Жом из рапса, выращенного в Республике Узбекистан, содержит практически все незаменимые аминокислоты. В выжимке из семян рапса обнаружено высокое содержание лейцина (2,28 г/100г), фениламина (1,2 г/100г), изолейцина (1,03 г/100г), метионина (0,87 г/100г), триптофана (0,431 г/100г). Это свидетельствует о том, что белки в выжимке из семян рапса имеют полноценный аминокислотный состав. Минеральный состав выжимки из семян рапса, выращенных в Республике Узбекистан, характеризуется высоким содержанием P-1116%, магния-465%, кальция 232,5%, калия-77,4%, цинка-9,38% и других макро- и микроэлементов. Полученные данные исследований свидетельствуют о целесообразности использования выжимки из семян рапса в национальных блюдах Узбекистана для повышения пищевой и биологической ценности.

Ключевые слова. выжимка из семян рапса, белок, аминокислотный состав, минеральный состав, макро- и микроэлементы, аминокислотный скор, незаменимые аминокислоты, биологическая ценность.

Introduction

Currently, one of the priorities of the government of the Republic of Uzbekistan is to provide the population with nutritious, high-protein food products. The average daily physiological requirement of a person for protein is constantly studied by the Ministry of Health of the Republic and is reflected in the decisions of the relevant mines and authorities. These indicators are indicative in nature, as they depend on the person's age, gender, nature of the work performed, physiological state, weather conditions, as well as environmental pollution. According to the indicative recommendations of WHO and FAO, the optimal protein requirement is 60-100 g per day or 12-15% of the total caloric intake. In the total amount of energy, protein of animal and plant origin accounts for 6-8% each. In terms of 1 kg of body weight, the protein requirement per day for an adult is on average about 1 g, while for children, depending on age, it ranges from 1.05 to 4.00 g [1].

Recommended protein standards developed by the Russian scientific school of nutrition include 73-120 g of protein per day for men and 60-90 g for women. Here, the lower limit is recommended for people not involved in physical labor, and the upper limit for people engaged in heavy physical labor [2].

For an adult man, the required level of protein consumption in terms of nitrogen is 9.0-9.2 g per day per 1 kg of body weight, and for persons suffering severe infections, surgical interventions, and having digestive and respiratory diseases, it can increase to 110-120 g, and in diabetics, its amount can reach 130-140 g [2,3].

There is a shortage of dietary protein all over the world, including in our republic. Scientists are looking for new sources of protein that correspond to complete protein and contain all the essential amino acids. One type of such raw material is rapeseed squeeze. Rapeseed is an oilseed crop and its cultivation solves the problem of providing vegetable oil, and the squeeze after obtaining the oil is a source of protein, vitamins, and aminokislotas [4] .

The use of rapeseed squeeze as an additive to food products helps to increase the nutritional and biological value without increasing the cost of these products [3] .

Taking into account the above, we decided to study the amino acid composition of protein and the content of aminokislotas in the squeeze of rapeseed seeds grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan [5] .

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study used the "Viking" variety grown in the fields of the Republic of Uzbekistan and cake obtained from rapeseed. (Figure (1,2)). In the experiments we used the squeeze obtained after obtaining the oil.

Fig. 1 rapeseed

Fig. 2 rapeseed squeeze

The amino acid composition of rapeseed squeeze proteins was studied according to GOST 32195-2013 [5].

Free forms of amino acids were extracted with dilute hydrochloric acid. Nitrogenous macromolecules extracted together with amino acids are precipitated with sulfosalicylic acid and filtered. The filtrate is adjusted to a value of 2.20 units. pH.

Amino acids are separated by ion exchange chromatography, reacted with ninhydrin, and their content is determined by photometric detection at a wavelength of 570 nm.

From (1.0000 $\pm$ 0.0002) g to (5.0000 $\pm$ 0.0002) g of sample is weighed on a scale and quantitatively transferred into a conical flask, 100.0 cm³ of extraction solution is added. The

mixture is stirred for 60 minutes using a magnetic stirrer, allowed to settle, then 10.0 cm³ of the supernatant is pipetted into a beaker with a capacity of 100 cm³.

While stirring, add 5.0 cm³ of sulfosalicylic acid and continue stirring with a magnetic stirrer for 5 minutes. The solution is filtered or spun or centrifuged to remove precipitate. Place 10.0 cm³ of the resulting solution in a glass with a capacity of 100 cm³ and adjust the acidity of the solution to 2.20 units. pH sodium using hydroxide solution. Transfer quantitatively into a volumetric flask of the appropriate volume (necessary for chromatography) and adjust the volume of the solution to the mark with citrate buffer.

If an internal standard is used, add 1.00 cm³ of internal standard for every 100 cm³ of the final volume of solution and make the volume to the mark with citrate buffer.

Before chromatography, the temperature of the extract or hydrolyzate is brought to room temperature. Stir the mixture and filter the required amount through a membrane filter. The resulting clear solution is used for ion exchange chromatography (HPLC equipment).

Sample injection can be done manually or automatically. It is important that equal amounts ($\pm 0.5\%$) of standard and sample solution are injected into the column, except when using an internal standard (for chromatographic systems requiring low sodium concentrations) and when the ratio of amino acids in standard and sample solutions should be as low as possible closer.

The peak areas of the standard and sample are measured for each amino acid.

The amino acid content in the analyzed sample, w , g / kg, is calculated using the formula [5]

$$W = \frac{A_0 * c * M * V_0}{A_0 * m * 1000};$$

Where A_0 is the peak area of the amino acid in the hydrolyzate and extract;

C - molar concentration of amino acids in a standard solution, mol/dm³;

M - molecular weight of amino acids

V_0 - total volume of hydrolyzate or calculated total volume of diluted extract, cm³;

A_c is the peak area of an amino acid in a standard solution;

m is the mass of the analyzed sample (adjusted for the initial mass for dry and or fat-free samples), g;

100 is the conversion factor for volume units;

The amino acid score was calculated according to the method of H. Mitchell and R. Block.

The study of the aminokislota composition of rapeseed squeeze grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan was carried out using the atomic absorption method using a solar atomic absorption spectrometer. S 2 [6].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

As we indicated above, today the big problem that needs to be solved is providing the country's population with high-protein food products. Various sources are considered as a source of protein to meet needs. These are plant or animal raw materials. One of the promising areas for providing protein to the country's population is rapeseed squeeze. As shown by the literature analysis, thanks to the work of breeders, rapeseed varieties were created, with a small amount of erucic acid (0-2%) and glucosinylates (less than 20 micrograms) called two-zero (oo), and “ ooo ” varieties of rapeseed, with yellow seeds (with a low content of not only erucic acid, glucosinolates , but also fiber) contributed to an increase in rapeseed crops and its processing of Viking and Ruyan varieties. All of the above varieties have a low acid and glucosinylates content; in the future, the area under rapeseed will be increased. This increase in the area under rapeseed will help solve problems with providing the population with vegetable oil, and the processing of secondary raw materials will serve to solve the problem of protein supply.

As you know, the quality of a protein is determined by its amino acid profile .

Oilseed proteins have a well-balanced amino acid composition, in particular rapeseed proteins. We studied the amino acid composition of rapeseed proteins in the laboratories of the Institute of Certification and Standardization.

For the most complete picture , we compared the amino acid composition of oilseed cakes (Table 1).

Compound irreplaceable amino acids cakes oilseeds crops

Table 1 .

No.	Irreplaceable amino acids	Cake sunflower variety Vanguard	Cake linen variety Issikulsky	Cake camelina variety Omich	rapeseed cake (Uzbekistan) mg/100g
	Valin	1,7	2,02	2,38	1,42
	Isoleucine	7,7	1,51	0,99	1,03
	Leucine	13,5	2,43	2,19	2,28
	Lysine	12,9	1,63	1,76	1,87
	Treanine	13,7	1,16	1,40	1,46
	Methionine	8,4	0,45	0,63	0,87
	Phenicalanine	11,3	1,35	1,78	1,20
	Tryptophan	4,4	0,59	0,33	0,43

As the analysis of the data in Table 1 shows .

cake contains all the essential amino acids of the crops [6].

Data on the amino acid composition of rapeseed cakes in comparison with soybean cakes are given in Table 2. [6].

Table 2

Amino acid composition of rapeseed squeezes

Names of indicators, units of measurement	Test results			Regulatory document (methodology) for test methods)
	Amino acid content of soybean meal	Amino acid content in rapeseed squeeze	Amino acid content in	

		g / 100g protein	rapeseed squeeze of Belarusian selection	
Protein, %	34.6	36.2	-	GOST 13496.4-2019
	Nonessential amino acids			
Alanin	2.11	1.73	2.04	GOST 32195-2013
Aspartic acid	5.66	2.72	4.88	
Glycine	2,078	1.7	1.66	
Glutamic acid	8.7	6.26	7.98	
Proline	2.62	2.11	2.77	
Serin	2.60	1.41	1.92	
Tyrosine	1.70	0.87	0.71	
Cysteine	0.724	0.46	0.20	
	Essential amino acids			
Arginine	3.44	1.84	0.74	GOST 32195-2013
Valin	2.24	1.42	4.3	
Histidine	1.21	1.03	0.54	
Isoleucine	2.18	1.03	2.08	
Leucine	3.66	2.28	3.00	
Lysine	2.99	1.87	1.82	
Methionine	0.406	0.87	0.001	
Threonine	1.95	1.46	2.2	
Tryptophan	0.65	0.431	0.40	
Phenylalanine	2.24	1.2	1.95	

Data analysis table. 2 shows that in rapeseed squeeze protein, almost all the amino acids of soy protein are present. Rapeseed seed squeeze contains a high content of leucine (2.28 g / 100 g), phenylalanine (1.2 g / 100 g), isoleucine (1.03 g / 100 g). It also contains methionine (0.87 g / 100 g), tryptophan (0.431 g / 100 g). This indicates that rapeseed squeeze protein has a complete amino acid composition.

As we indicated above, the main goal of this research work is the use of rapeseed squeeze as an additive to increase the nutritional and biological value of the national dishes of the Republic of Uzbekistan. As an analysis of the amino acid composition of protein squeeze from rapeseed grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan shows, it contains up to 2.28% leucine, which is an essential amino acid that is not synthesized by the cells of the body, but enters the body exclusively from proteins that are part of food. Lack or absence of leucine in the human body can lead to weight loss, development and growth arrest, as well as metabolic disorders [7].

Another essential amino acid of rapeseed squeeze protein is lysine 1.87%. Lysine is a relatively metabolically inert amino acid and does not actively participate in the reversible processes of transamination or deamination, but plays an important role in the formation of hemoglobin and increases capillary permeability.

Lysine deficiency promotes the development of dental caries [7]. Also, a high content of essential amino acids valine, threonine, phenylalanine, of which

threonine promotes the growth of skeletal mice, is part of immune proteins and a number of digestive enzymes, plays a major role in the synthesis of purines and glycine, serves as a source of energy, and phenylalanine is converted into tyrosine and adrenaline. Thyroxine, formed from tyrosine, plays an important role in the activity of the thyroid gland, increasing its functional ability and valine, which maintains the proper level of serotonin and, together with leucine and isoleucine, serves as a high source of energy in the body [8].

Squeeze protein from rapeseed seeds grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan also contains methionine [0.87%], tryptophan [0.43%], isoleucine [1.03 g], which are also essential and play an important role in the functioning of the human body. For example, methionine is an amino acid containing sulfur and plays an important role in the activity of the nervous system. It ensures normal transportation of fat from the liver and its antitoxic function. A distinctive feature of the amino acids in rapeseed meal protein is that they contain sulfur and this is necessary for maintaining normal weight and human performance, because if its quantity is insufficient, the biological value of proteins decreases. The amino acid composition of rapeseed squeeze proteins is practically balanced and it has a positive effect on their digestibility. The consumption of dietary proteins in food generally has a positive effect on people's health. By supplying the body with essential amino acids, protein products are a source of dietary fiber that can form structural complexes with the therapeutic and physiological function of influencing intestinal motility and regulating cholesterol levels in the blood. Plant proteins reduce the level of serum lipids in patients with hyperlipidemia and, in connection with this, interest in replacing animal proteins with plant proteins is increasing [8].

It is known that the lack of at least one essential amino acid causes a negative nitrogen balance, disruption of the nervous system, growth arrest and incomplete absorption of others.

The dependence of the functioning of the body on the amount of essential amino acids is used to determine the biological value of proteins using chemical methods. We calculated the amino acid score of proteins in squeeze from rapeseed seeds grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan using the method of H. Mitchell and R. Blok. (Mitchell, Blok, 1946) [6]. In accordance with which the amino acid composition of the studied samples is compared with the amino acid composition of the ideal protein adopted by the FAO-WAO expert committee in 1973. [10] by determining the amino acid score. Scor is expressed as a percentage or as a dimensionless value and represents the ratio of the content of an essential amino acid (EA) in the protein under study to its amount in the reference protein. When calculating the speed, the formula is as follows

$$AKS = \frac{(M2 \text{ amino acid B12 protein})}{(M2 \text{ amino acid B12 standard})} \times 100$$

Table 3

**Results of amino acid protein of rapeseed squeeze grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan
FAO / WHO (1973)**

Amino acids	Adults FAO/WAO in 1973	Content of essential amino acids in rapeseed squeeze	Amino acid score %
Isoleucine	40	1.03	2.57
Leucine	70	2.28	3.25
Lysine	55	1.87	3.40

Methionine	35	0.87	2.48
Phenylalanine	60	1.20	2.00
Threonine	40	1.46	3.66
Tryptophan	10	0.431	4.31
Valin	50	1.42	2.84

Since rapeseed is grown in many countries of the world, we decided to compare the amino acid composition of the protein of rapeseed squeeze grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Belarusian selection.

Fig.3. Comparative analysis of the amino acid composition of protein squeeze from rapeseeds grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan and Belarusian selection [9].

As shown by a comparative analysis of the amino acid composition of the protein, squeeze from rapeseed seeds grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan and Belarusian selection contains almost all essential amino acids, but in terms of quantitative composition it is inferior to squeeze from Belarusian seeds [9].

Conclusions: Analysis of the amino acid composition of rapeseed squeeze obtained from rapeseed grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan shows that it contains all eight essential amino acids. Rapeseed squeeze contains a high content of leucine - 3.66%, lysine - 2.99%, valine - 2.24%, isoleucine - 2.24%, threonine - 1.99%, as well as partially replaceable arginine - 3.44%. This all indicates the high biological value of this raw material. The study also examined the aminokislota composition of rapeseed squeeze. Rapeseed squeeze is rich in aminokislotas, and the high content of P, K, Ca, Mg Zn, Fe, Na and other elements shows that it can serve as a good source of food fortification and does not increase the cost of these dishes.

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Food chemistry. Nechaev AP, Traubenberg SE, Kochetkova AA, etc. Under. ed . AP Nechaeva.-SPb.: GIORD, 2001.-592 p.
2. Skurukhin I.M., Shaternikov . VA How to eat properly.-2nd. ed., revised. And home. - M.: Agropromizdat , 1986.-256 p.

3. Pakhomova ON Development and use of a functional food fortifier from rapeseed squeeze. Diss . on sois . scientist step. Candidate of Technical Sciences. Eagle. 2014.-162p.
4. Vasilenko ZV Characteristics of the chemical composition of rapeseed squeeze, variety “Neman” of Belarusian selection. ZV Vasilenko, VI Nikulin, TV Trofimenko. Bulletin of the Belarusian State University of Food and Chemical Technologies. -2022, - N 2 [33]. pp. 27-36.
5. GOST 32195-2013 Feed compound. Method for determining amino acid content.
6. Block, RJ, Mitchell, HH (1946) The Correlation of the Amino Acid composition of Proteins with Nutritiv Value. Nutrition Abstracts Reviews, 16, 219-278.
7. Atomic adsorption spectrometer SOLAAR S 2 N 228 U -02. Manufacturer: Thermo Company Elemental » USA .
8. Renyazeva TV Functional properties of protein products from rapeseed and camelina squeezes. Equipment and technology of food production. Volume 15, Edition 4, Kemerovo. 2009 .- 4 pages.
9. Toshev AD Prospects for the use of rapeseed squeeze in the nutrition of athletes / Toshev AD, Zhuravleva ND, Yarygina ES, Velyamov MT Pozdnyakovsky VM Man. Sport. Medicine. 2018. T.18. T 1. P 115-124.